

Menstrual Health Practices of Female Workers: A Study of Kodala Tea Estate of Bangladesh

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Abstract

Maintaining hygiene during menstruation is very important for women. Working women do not always get an adequate environment to practice hygiene. Workers are most deprived in various socio-economic contexts, including health, in the tea plantations of Bangladesh. In the garden area, female workers are considered a vulnerable population due to the lack of an environment to follow menstrual hygiene, inadequate education and knowledge, low income, etc. The study was conducted on the menstrual health and hygiene practices of female workers in the Kodala tea estate area in Rangunia Upazila, Chattogram, Bangladesh. Following a mixed method, the study explored the hygiene practices, work environment, and benefits and challenges faced by female workers during menstruation. The study showed that most of the female workers are indifferent to hygiene practices. Lack of awareness, a poor environment, a poor standard of living, and low wages have been found to have a negative impact on menstrual health and hygiene practices. It is found that 90% of female workers suffer from a variety of health issues as a result of poor menstrual hygiene, such as genital itching, sexual intercourse pain, increased white discharge, etc. 98% of female workers find it difficult to work during menstruation. The study recommended the establishment of proper healthcare facilities to ensure health safety for female workers. Simultaneously, a better standard of living along with regular awareness campaigns can provide a sustainable and healthy work environment for the female workers of the tea estate.

Keywords: Menstrual hygiene, tea estate, female workers, health practices.

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1. Introduction

In today's developing countries, health and sanitation are among the most serious issues as there is a considerable lack of health and hygiene education among the people. Mostly, this lack of health awareness impacts marginalized communities like women working in the tea estates of Bangladesh. Although health is one of the basic rights, ensuring adequate health care for working women has become a challenging issue these days. Despite all the progress in women's empowerment, their health is so neglected, especially during menstruation. One of the most challenging communities suffering from unhygienic menstrual health in Bangladesh is the female workers at the tea estates.

Bangladesh, one of the largest tea producers in the world hosts around 3.6 lacs workers in 166 commercial tea estates (UN, 2021). Female workers account for about two-thirds of the total workers at the tea estates. For generations, women workers have been working in tea gardens. Starting from collecting leaves to spending their whole life in the tea estates has become the routine of their life. Despite contributing to the sector continuously, female workers lack socioeconomic appreciation as well as face regular challenges in fulfilling almost all basic needs (Ahmed et. al., 2010). In particular, healthcare is an arena where they have been deprived of necessary facilities and are subject to exploitation. Among many challenges, they do not have proper education, healthcare facilities, safe water, hygienic sanitation systems, and housing facilities (Hassan, 2014; Kamruzzaman et. al., 2015). Nevertheless, the lack of healthcare awareness and facilities impacts their reproductive and menstrual health at manifold.

Health care of women workers is an important issue, especially during menstruation since women workers have to continue working during this period. Menstruation is a normal part of every woman's life cycle. Maintaining menstrual health and cleanliness is a major part of women's reproductive health. Failure to proper hygienic practices regarding menstrual health can cause various physical problems that affect their daily life in a negative manner (Kalita, 2020). Female workers in the tea gardens work for 8-10 hours a day which usually increases during the leaf collection period. However, these female workers do not maintain hygienic practices to ensure proper menstrual health due to a lack of awareness and adequate facilities. Most of the female workers wear dirty clothes during menstruation. Since their standard of living is quite low, they fail to adopt the practices that can help them keep sound menstrual health (Chowdhury et al. 2011). Although the tea estate authorities have tried to establish some regular facilities to aid the workers in general, they are not specific and adequate for the female workers (Kamruzzaman et. al., 2015; Sarkar et. al., 2016).

In many cases, women's health has not received special attention. A few studies or reports generate interest, but they are insufficient. Women have always been disenfranchised in our society. The image of tea gardens is no exception. In a study conducted by Barsha and Kalita (2016) to examine menstrual health and taboos among tea plantation laborers in *Durrung* Tea Estate, Assam, it was found that in a patriarchal society, women are discriminated against. Although menstruation is a normal process, it has become a problem of religious, cultural, and gender discrimination. Menstruation is considered unclean and dirty and the ignorance and unawareness among female workers in the tea state were evident.

At the same time, several studies have identified a lack of available resources for safe sanitation and hygiene in the estate areas. Tea plantation workers are deprived of adequate latrine facilities,

water supply, waste management, and housing facilities (Chowdhury et al., 2011; Amiya, et al., 2010). As there is no tube well for drinking water, the local government has not taken any initiative to supply clean water. Abanyie et al. (2019) conducted a study on menstrual health management among women working in the formal and informal sectors. The study revealed that among women in the formal sector, 24% share a washroom with male colleagues, and 12% share a washroom. There is also a high level of insecurity in the informal sector, as a larger percentage (84%) of women workers share wash facilities with men. Since the tea plantation workers are part of the informal sector, the lack of adequate sanitation facilities creates a negative impact on their menstrual health.

Apart from the absence of proper sanitation facilities in the tea garden areas, the female workers have been facing a few challenges in their living and working conditions. One key challenge is a lack of awareness regarding significant areas like their health, rights, working policy, education, and economic facilities (Hassan, 2014; Chowdhury et al., 2011; Amiya et al., 2010). They lack health awareness and no training on practicing safe menstrual health is being given in the garden areas. Thus, female workers often have to drop working hours as well as days that impact their earnings (Amiya et al., 2010). Moreover, women workers in tea estates are not aware of their rights. There is no enforcement of laws for female tea workers in terms of sexual harassment policy, maternity leave, working hours, pay structure, and so on (Hassan, 2014). Additionally, due to superstition or ignorance, many workers still follow traditional medical methods instead of modern medical care. Even if medical care is available in the work areas, many are reluctant to accept it. Due to a lack of menstrual awareness and financial weakness, these workers tend to use cloth instead of pads during menstruation (Priya et al., 2017).

Nevertheless, lack of education is considered one of the significant reasons behind such lack of awareness among female tea workers. More importantly, lack of knowledge about hygiene and cleanliness often results in poor hygiene and the female workers in tea estates do not have any knowledge about maintaining their menstrual health (Saikia, 2017; Chowdhury et al. 2011). Studies identified that in general, women have a lower tendency to know about menstrual hygiene practices. Studies found the average literacy rate of female workers in the tea estates of Bangladesh is around 35 percent (Sarman & Karalam, 2019; Ruma & Dipak, 2014; Bosumatari & Goyari, 2013). A study by Ali et al. (2020) found that only 28.4% of the general population of Karachi, Pakistan, and 29.4% of the healthcare workers knew the correct position of menstrual and absorbent pads. Such scenarios can be changed by arranging awareness activities led by the government and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The activities can include training, knowledge knowledge-sharing workshops, and providing basic education. However, there has been no evidence of any awareness activities related to proper maintenance of sanitation and menstrual hygiene among female tea workers (Chowdhury et al. 2011).

One important factor behind the unawareness and disinterest in knowing and practicing menstrual hygiene among female workers is lower economic status. Poor wages prevent them from availing sanitary napkins and necessary instruments of hygiene (Rajbangshi, et al., 2020; Nair et al., 2012). At the same time, their accommodation facilities are below standard with poor sanitation facilities that hinder their regular health practices. This substandard management of health practices of working women affects their work performance negatively. Hennegan et al. (2021) found in their study that 15% of working women miss work during menstruation whereas 41% of working women do not like to work during menstruation. Moreover, Sommer, Kjellén, and Pensulo (2013)

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found that in low-income countries there are several challenges to hygiene during menstruation. Lack of privacy and space to change menstrual materials, lack of adequate water, and failure to ensure sanitation their findings revealed problems with menstrual waste disposal, inadequate sanitation, and lack of knowledge.

Overall, the existing literature identified several factors behind the poor socioeconomic condition of female workers in the tea estates in Bangladesh. However, different tea estates have different cultures and practices. Although the number of tea estates in Bangladesh is quite high, one common attribute of all of the estates is the major portion of female workers. Previous studies have addressed the common concerns of livelihood of the female workers but very few have identified the menstrual practices of female workers and the impact of their menstrual health on their overall health. This study focused on addressing that knowledge gap by exploring the current menstrual health practices of the female workers in Kodala Tea Estate of Chattogram district, identifying the major challenges they face regarding maintaining their menstrual health, and providing some policy recommendations to adhere to those challenges.

2. Methodology

2.1 Method

The study followed a mixed research method incorporating both quantitative and qualitative tools for research. The researchers collected both primary and secondary data for a clear understanding of the practices and challenges regarding the menstrual health and hygiene of female workers of tea estates in Bangladesh. An extensive literature review was conducted to lay the foundation of the research problem identified in this study. The research area for this study was the *Kodala Tea Garden* which is situated in *Kodala Union* of *Chattogram District*.

2.2 Sampling and Data Collection

The study collected primary data from 70 female workers working in the *Kodala tea estate* following a random sampling method. These 70 respondents were selected based on a few criteria such as age, gender, years of working in the tea state, etc. A survey was conducted with a semi-structured questionnaire containing both open-ended and close-ended questions. At the same time, for a detailed understanding of the challenges in a group setting, 5 Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) have been conducted with 40 women aged between 25 years to 40 years. Moreover, since there are male workers along with the female workers in the tea estate. In order to understand the perception of the male workers, 10 interviews with semi-structured questionnaires were conducted. The secondary data collected from different research articles, reports, books, and web documents have contributed to finding the existing research gap regarding the research problem and relating the findings to scenarios of other tea estates in Bangladesh that have already been explored. All the interviews were recorded with the informed consent of the respondents.

2.3 Data Analysis

The data analysis of the study includes the transcription of raw data from an audio source to text, translation of the collected data into English, and data cleaning. Once the data was sorted, analysis was conducted in two ways. Firstly, the quantitative data were statistically analyzed based on the responses and secondly, the qualitative data were analyzed based on the thematic approach. Altogether, the results were presented by combining these two approaches under separate themes originating from the data that tried to answer the assorted research questions in the study.

3. Findings

3.1 Age group

Workers of different ages can be seen in the tea plantations of Bangladesh. There are many families in the garden area that put their children to work at an early age. The biggest reason behind this is poverty. They have been working in the garden for generations. Among the interviewed 70 female workers, 43 percent are from the age group of 21-30 years which is the highest (Table 1). The next largest group is constituted by female workers of age group 31-40 accounting for 37 percent of the respondents. Among the rest, 17 percent are of 11-20 years and 3 percent are over 40 years old.

Table 1: Age group of female workers

The age group of the Respondents (years)	Frequency	Percentage
11-20	12	17.2%
21-30	30	42.9%
31-40	26	37.1%
40 and above	2	2.8%

3.2 Education Level of Respondents

Most of the female workers in the study are illiterate. However, the majority of them can sign their name which constitutes about 53 percent of the total respondents (Table 2). Only 11.5 percent of the respondents have completed primary education and the rest of them cannot even sign their name.

Table 2: Education Level

Level of Education	Frequency	Percentage
Valid Nil	25	35.7
Name and Signature	37	52.9
Primary	8	11.4

3.3 Years of experience

All of the tea garden workers were born in the tea garden. Most of the respondents in this study have been working here for more than 10 years. The share of female workers working in the tea estate for 21-30 years is the highest (51.5 percent) among the respondents whereas the share of

workers working for 11-20 years is 40 percent. The study was conducted during the leaf-picking season accounting for 90–95 percent of the workers actively engaged in leaf-picking. The rest were involved in weed-cutting, tree planting, and maintenance.

Table 3: Years of experience of the respondents

Years worked in the tea garden	Frequency	Percentage
1-10	6	8.5
11-20	28	40.0
21-30	36	51.5

3.4 Economic Condition

It has been found that the wages of workers in the tea estate are very low. The daily target of the workers is to pick 24–25 kg of leaves per day for which they are paid 120 BDT. If they pick more leaves than the target, they are paid an additional 3 TK per kg. As a result, many people pick 40 to 50 kg of leaves per day.

Table 4: Average monthly income of the respondents

Average Monthly Income (BDT)	Frequency	Percentage
0-3000	56	80.0
3000-5000	11	15.7
Above 5000	3	4.3

It is evident from Table 4 that 80 percent of the respondents earn less than BDT 3000 monthly by working in the tea estate. Only 3 female workers among the respondents earn more than BDT 5000 which constitutes only 4.3 percent. Moreover, none of the workers have a minimum income for fulfilling their basic needs as the data depicts.

3.5 Menstrual Health and Hygiene of the Workers

In the tea gardens, female workers are found to be the most powerful workforce. As a percentage, their numbers are much higher than those of men. But they are deprived of proper health care. Due to a lack of proper sanitation facilities, their health risks are increasing day by day. Moreover, during menstruation, working becomes difficult for female workers. Since the tea garden areas are very large, collecting tea leaves from different parts of the garden takes up a huge toll on the physique of the female workers during menstruation. Unfortunately, the sanitation facilities are situated only at a central place in the garden causing the workers to walk a long distance several times of the day. During menstruation, it becomes more challenging for female workers to walk that much and use the facilities.

In the tea gardens, female workers tend to use traditional processes instead of modern ones during menstruation. The study found that 94 percent of the female workers use clothes during menstruation whereas only 6 percent of them use sanitary pads (Table 5). At the same time, they do not change the material even when necessary. Almost 50 percent of them do not change the material they use once a day. Among the rest, 32 percent change their material once a day, 14 percent change twice a day, and the other 4 percent change thrice a day (Table 5). Lack of proper

education related to menstrual health and hygiene is a key reason behind this. At the same time, inadequate changing facilities in the workplace are a major factor for their reluctance to change sanitary items while working.

Table 5: Menstrual health-related information

Items related to Menstrual health	Responses	Share of responses (In percent)
Material use during menstruation	Clothes	94
	Disposable Sanitary Napkins	6
Changing material in a day during menstruation	One time	32
	Two Times	14
	Three Times	4
	Not even once	50
Sanitation and Latrine facilities in households	No Latrines	15
	Ordinary Latrines (Open)	80
	Sanitary Latrines	5
Menstrual health-related problems	Genital itching	33
	Discharge of white fluid	15
	Pain during intercourse	43

Moreover, their housing areas are situated quite far from their workplace where they could go and change. Most of the workers live in the designated quarter for them near the tea estates. The tea estate authority is responsible for providing them with healthy sanitation facilities. Unfortunately, only 5 percent of the female workers mentioned having sanitary latrines at their home which they built at their own expense and 15 percent mentioned having no latrines at all. The rest 80 percent own ordinary latrine facilities at the household level (Table 5). The garden authorities assured to provide sanitary latrines to all but no such initiative has been seen yet. Along with the latrine problem, inadequate water supply disrupts the health of the female workers. In the quarters, the workers get water supply from shared tube wells. They often have to use water from rivers due to the scarcity. Due to this lack of adequate facilities, female workers often fall ill, and the unhygienic practices adhere to continuous physical problems like genital itching, discharge of white fluid, etc.

3.6 Health facilities provided by the Tea Estate Authority

The authority of the tea estate is supposed to provide healthcare facilities for their workers. In line with that, there is already a medical center established in the area. But the center is not enriched as the workers can access only first aid and some general medicines. Before the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak, an MBBS doctor used to serve at the medical center twice weekly. However, in recent times, the service is not available. As a result, only 56 percent of the respondents mentioned about the availability of the medical services provided by the garden authority (Table 6). Interestingly,

only 13 percent of the female workers who have availed services from the medical center have shown their satisfaction with the services. This showcases the lack of sincerity and facilities in the medical center provided by the garden authority.

Table 6: Healthcare facilities provided by the Tea Estate Authority

Healthcare facilities	Responses	Share of responses (In percent)
Availability of medical services provided by the garden authority	Available	56
	Not available	44
Satisfaction level with the medical services provided by the garden authority	Satisfied	13
	Not satisfied	87
Allowance by the authority for healthcare	Not Provided	100
Impact of the work environment on menstrual health	Positive	13
	Negative	87

More specifically, there is no separate health assistance from the garden authorities during menstruation as mentioned by the female workers. The female workers have to work for 6-8 hours on average even during the menstrual cycle. The pressure intensifies during leaf picking season as the workers work for more than 10 hours during that time. Unfortunately, the workers do not get any separate health service other than just basic treatments in the medical center. They have to move to the city to get better healthcare. However, all of the female respondents have mentioned that they do not get any financial allowance from the authorities for accessing better healthcare. As a result, the negative impact of the work environment on their menstrual health goes unnoticed and uncared for as pointed out by the respondents. Apart from better medical care, some of the respondents mentioned that there is a need for various awareness programs for women on various health-related issues.

3.7 Other facilities provided by the NGOs

The female workers mentioned that they do not have any labor union in their tea estate. As a result, often their rights, demands, and needs go unnoticed and uninformed to the estate authorities. Even the male respondents acknowledged the lack of enough wage, basic healthcare, inadequate menstrual and maternal health care, a lack of education, and prejudice. Interestingly, despite many NGOs working to ensure the healthcare of the workers in various industries, no NGO is working on the healthcare of the tea estate workers in the area. The female workers mentioned past activities of a project by BRAC where the NGO used to support the workers by giving them healthcare services at their homes. However, for the last three years, the workers have not gotten that support from BRAC as well.

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4. Discussion

Despite permanent female workers accounting for more than half of the workers in the tea estate working for generations, they lack basic healthcare facilities. The estate authority has failed to provide them with the necessary tools for protecting and supporting their health. At the same time, they have a considerable lack of sincerity regarding their own health due to ignorance. The key reason behind their ignorance is their lack of education. More than one-third of the respondents in this study are illiterate. They never attended any educational facilities and do not have adequate knowledge regarding taking care of their health and hygiene. Although a few of them have basic primary education, taking care of their health requires knowledge that is not provided at that level, especially menstrual health. Another key reason behind their lack of sincerity in health and hygiene is chronic poverty. Their average income accounts for so little that they can hardly ensure proper subsistence let alone healthcare. Moreover, their prior concern is mostly living rather than maintaining the basic standard of living.

It is evident that a low level of education and financial instability have a major influence on their efforts to maintain proper health and hygiene. However, inadequate facilities and zero interventions provided by the authorities have a significant contribution to the poor practices of hygiene of the estate workers. The authorities are supposed to create awareness and provide facilities to ensure the effective implementation of health and hygiene practices by the workers. Especially, since more than half of the workers are female, ensuring proper facilities focusing on the menstrual health of the female workers is a must in the estate area. Unfortunately, this is where the estate authorities have failed to provide any necessary support. Not only do they have any establishment or facilities to support the requirements of female workers during menstruation, but also, they also do not undertake any awareness creation activities for the female workers.

The female workers do not use any sanitary napkins during their menstruation, they hardly change the cloth or the material they use during their menstruation and they are mostly not integral to maintaining cleanliness. Evidently, working during menstruation harms their productivity as well as their health. They have to work for 6-8 hours on a daily average even during their menstruation which has a deteriorating impact on their health due to the nature of their work. Unfortunately, the estate does not have any facilities such as toilets, clean water, etc. to provide them necessary support to ensure their menstrual healthcare. Their ignorance regarding menstrual hygiene along with the lack of such facilities has created carelessness among the workers in maintaining their menstrual health.

Another area where female workers are deprived of healthcare facilities is at their household level. They also lack standard sanitation facilities, hygienic water, and adequate toilets at the quarters provided by the tea estate authority. The toilets are shared by two to three families and that deteriorates the cleanliness of the toilet as these are only ordinary latrines. At the same time, due to a lack of quality water facilities in their quarters, they have to endure several physical problems which heavily include problems in their reproductive health such as genital itching and discharge of white fluid. Since the estate authority failed to provide adequate healthcare support in the medical center established in the garden area, the female workers did not get any satisfactory treatment without moving to the city. However, they cannot afford the treatment in the city due to

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their poor economic condition. If the facilities in the working area are not improved, the reproductive health of the female workers can deteriorate further in the near future. At the same time, no NGOs are working as well to create healthcare awareness among the garden workers which could improve the situation.

Based on the findings of the study, it is evident that to ensure proper menstrual health practices by the female workers in the tea estate, some major interventions are required. The estate authority needs to ensure better medical services at the medical center situated in the garden area including the regular presence of experienced physicians, and nurses, and the availability of better medical equipment. Simultaneously, the authority should provide the workers with better accommodations containing standard sanitation facilities and water supply for each family. Improving the sanitation facilities in the areas where female workers work is a must so that they are encouraged and ensured of healthy menstrual practices. However, the initiation of such practices will need awareness among the workers in the first place. This is an area where different NGOs can work besides the estate authority. Nonetheless, without proper education, this ignorance and unhygienic tendencies will continue over generations and that is why the authority needs to encourage the workers to ensure the education of their children and support them with accessing proper education facilities near that area. Lastly, due to low wages and poverty, women workers cannot follow hygiene rules during menstruation and for this reason, quick attention is recommended in revising the wage structure of the workers in the tea estate.

5. Conclusion

Bangladesh is one of the largest tea-producing countries in the world. This industry plays a major role in the country's growing economy. Despite the continuous growth of Bangladesh's tea industry, the socio-economic development of the tea plantation workers is not growing at all. Specially, female tea workers are lagging behind in many indicators including education, health, and social security. Due to the lack of proper management on the tea plantations, the living conditions of the female workers are deteriorating day by day. Health during menstruation is a very sensitive issue as it is directly related to reproduction. There is no substitute for good health when it comes to quality living. Menstrual health and hygiene are the most important factors influencing female workers' quality of life. However, the menstrual health situation in tea plantations is not satisfactory, and the ignorance and indifference of women workers lead to a worse situation.

The study recommends better healthcare facilities such as in-house hospitals, and specialized physicians in the hospitals on a regular basis to tend to the medical needs of the female workers. Especially, a female physician experienced in attending to patients with menstrual health will aid the female workers' specific needs regarding their menstrual health. At the same time, the provision of better medical equipment, nurses, etc. should be increased including ensuring healthcare during menstruation, antenatal and postnatal care. At the same time, their living standards must be improved by ensuring proper housing, adequate and improved sanitation facilities, establishing safe water sources, and separate washrooms for female workers in the garden area.

Moreover, their wage rate needs to be increased so that they can maintain a standard livelihood and ensure proper education and health for their future generations. However, to enhance their health consciousness, regular awareness campaigns need to be organized by the garden authorities as well as the local government and NGOs working in the locality. More importantly, the government needs to form a regulation to make the tea estate authorities accountable for ensuring proper basic needs for their workers. In addition to the prosperity of the tea industry, the socio-economic development of the workers is essential. The workers involved in the tea industry are known as marginalized groups. Focusing on them must be an integral part of the development of the economy. Moreover, ensuring individual protection for female workers during menstruation or maternity will enable their socioeconomic development.

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